

STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER BIAXIAL LOADS

M J Hinton*, P D Soden** and A S Kaddour**

* Defence Research Agency (DRA), Fort Halstead, Sevenoaks, Kent, TN14 7BP, UK.

** Applied Mechanics Division, UMIST, Sackville Street, Manchester, M60 1QD, UK.

ABSTRACT

Five well known failure criteria and one simple progressive model have been used in conjunction with laminate theory, which allows for nonlinear lamina shear behaviour, to predict the initial and final failure strengths of filament wound composite tubes. The predictions have been compared with experimental leakage and fracture stresses for $\pm 75^\circ$, $\pm 55^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ filament wound GRP tubes subjected to a wide range of biaxial stress systems including biaxial compression. In some cases the fracture strengths were a factor of 10 higher than the initial failure predictions. The simple progressive failure theory predictions gave the best agreement with the experimental results.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composites have gained widespread acceptance as practical engineering materials and therefore prediction of failure of laminated composites is important. Although there are many failure criteria[1] available for use, a failure criterion can only be considered, from a designer's viewpoint, to be useful if it can predict the strength of a wide range of laminates under a wide range of complex stress states. Unfortunately relatively few experimental investigations have determined the strength of laminates under a sufficiently wide range of biaxial or triaxial loading conditions to allow for the failure criteria and design methods to be validated by comparison with experimental results. One of the most extensive sets of published experimental data on a single type of laminate, namely $\pm\theta$ filament wound tubes, was from tests conducted by the authors[2], but that did not include any data for strength under biaxial or triaxial compression.

The objective of this paper is to show the extent to which selected failure analysis methods describe the previously published experimental data on the strength of $\pm 75^\circ$, $\pm 55^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ filament wound E-glass fibre/epoxy tubes and also to present experimental results for the strength of the $\pm 55^\circ$ filament wound tubes under various combinations of biaxial compression.

2. FAILURE CRITERIA

Of the numerous different failure criteria which are available for composite laminates[1], the five failure criteria which will be considered in this study are:-(a) Maximum stress[1], (b) Maximum strain[1], (c) Hill[3], (d) Tsai-Wu[4] and (e) Schneider[5]. These criteria are widely used by designers and all of the criteria require that the unidirectional properties of the lamina are known from a series of uniaxial tests. A typical set of properties for a unidirectional lamina is shown in Table (1).

TABLE (1) Mechanical properties of unidirectional glass/epoxy lamina for a fibre volume fraction V_f of 60%

Fibre	E-Glass fibre-SILENKA 071L, 1200tex				
Matrix	Epoxy resin- Ciba Geigy MY750/HY917/DY063 mixed in proportion 100:85:2				
Elastic constants		Ultimate Strengths		Thermal expansions	
E_L (GPa)	45.6	X_T (MPa)	1280	$\alpha_L \mu\epsilon/^\circ C$	8.6
E_T (GPa)	16.23	X_C (MPa)	525	$\alpha_T \mu\epsilon/^\circ C$	26.4
E_{LT} (GPa)	5.5*	Y_T (MPa)	40		
ν_{LT}	0.278	Y_C (MPa)	145		
		S (MPa)	73		

* This is the initial modulus and the non-linear shear stress strain τ_{LT} - γ_{LT} equation up to 4% strain is given by

$$\tau_{LT} = A \gamma_{LT}^4 + B \gamma_{LT}^3 + C \gamma_{LT}^2 + D \gamma_{LT} + E \text{ where } \tau_{LT} \text{ in MPa and } \gamma_{LT} \text{ in } \%$$

$$A = -0.484, B = 6.281, C = -30.966, D = 72.584, E = 0.031$$

The maximum stress and maximum strain criteria compare the stresses or strains in each lamina with the ultimate strength values for five separate modes of lamina failure, namely tension, compression or shear in directions parallel and transverse to the fibre.

The Hill criteria allows for interactions between the different stresses. The Tsai-Wu is a general theory which allows for interaction between direct and shear stresses and for differences between tensile and compressive strength but like the Hill criteria does not identify the failure mode. The Schneider theory allows for two modes of failure, resin damage and fibre fracture.

3 PROGRESSIVE FAILURE MODELLING

In the laminate theory employed here the load is increased incrementally and allowance is made for thermal stresses arising from curing and for non-linear shear behaviour by decreasing the shear modulus at each load increment. To determine the ultimate strength of a laminate some form of progressive failure analysis is required. In the simple form of progressive failure analysis employed here, the stresses in every lamina are calculated at each step and the chosen failure criterion applied. If failure is detected, the elastic properties for the failed lamina are recalculated following the rules shown in Table (2) and the new structural stiffness of the laminate determined.

TABLE 2 Description of modes of failure and assumed stiffness after initial failure

Mode no	Mode	Modified elastic constants	
1	Longitudinal tension	$E_L = 0$	$\nu_{LT} = 0$
2	Longitudinal compression	$E_L = 0$	$\nu_{LT} = 0$
3	Transverse tension	$E_T = 0$	$\nu_{TL} = 0$
4	Transverse compression	$E_T = 0$	$\nu_{TL} = 0$
5	Intralaminar Shear	$G_{LT} = 0$	

Further load increments can be made until another mode of failure is indicated. The failure detection, stiffness modification, loading increment pattern is repeated until two modes of failure have occurred in any one layer. This is the point at which complete failure of the lamina is assumed to take place. The lamina stiffness matrix is then singular, implying that gross deformation would occur.

Here only the maximum stress criteria coupled with the simplified progressive failure model shown in Table 2 are used to analyze the strength of $\pm\theta$ angle ply laminates. The results for the $\pm 55^\circ$ tubes and several other laminates are being analyzed by leading workers using other progressive failure models but the same lamina properties[6].

4. THE BIAxIAL STRENGTH TESTS

The specimens, Fig 1, were filament wound tubes, usually 100mm internal diameter, 350mm long, and wall thicknesses of 1mm for tests carried out under internal pressure and axial loading. The fibre volume fraction was 60%. In some of the axial compression tests, the specimens wall thickness was increased up to 5mm to evaluate the influence of shell buckling. The ends of the specimens had additional reinforcement carefully designed to avoid end failures and excessive stress concentrations. The ratio of internal pressure to axial load was usually maintained constant in any given test to obtain a fixed ratio (SR) of circumferential to axial stress in the gauge length. In some cases the tubes were lined with an elastomeric coating. The test techniques have been described in detail elsewhere[2].

Fig 1 Biaxial tension test rig, Ref[2]

The form of the test rig used in the recent biaxial compression tests is shown in Fig.2. The specimens were also filament wound tubes with a winding angle of $\pm 55^\circ$, diameter 51mm or 100mm and radius to thickness ratios down to 3.5. The fibre volume fraction was 70%. No grips were needed in the biaxial compression tests. The specimens were designed to avoid failure by buckling. Inner fittings were carefully designed in order to minimise stress concentration near the tube ends. The test rig, Fig.2, consists basically of a thick cylindrical steel pressure vessel with bolted end plates (1,2,6), specimen (5), end plugs and pistons (3,4,7) and a tension/compression bar (8). Most tests were carried out using a testing machine to pull or push the bar, depending upon the stress ratio sought. For tests

Fig 2 Biaxial compression test rig

carried out without using the machine (no tension/compression bar), the specimens were subjected to external radial pressure with an equal end pressure, and the ratio of hoop to axial stresses achieved was $SR = -2/-1$. In order to achieve stress ratios of less than $-2/-1$, the axial compressive load was increased, proportional to the radial pressure, by applying tension to the bar using the testing machine. For tests with stress ratios greater than $-2/-1$, the end pressure was partially opposed by applying compression to the bar. In both cases, the ratio of end force to the radial pressure was kept constant in any given test.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The failure stresses measured in the experiments in which $\pm 75^\circ$, $\pm 55^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ filament wound tubes were subjected to various combinations of circumferential tension and axial tension or compression are plotted in Figs(3-8). The results have been discussed in a previous publication[2].

Biaxial compression test results

A series of tests have been carried out recently using the test procedure described in Section 4 to determine the strength of thick $\pm 55^\circ$ filament wound tubes under various combinations of external pressure and axial load. The circumferential and axial failure stresses for these specimens are plotted in Fig(6) together with the previous biaxial test results. The experimental failure stresses were those at the inner surface of specimens using thick orthotropic cylinder theory. All the specimens for which the results are presented in Fig(6) failed by crushing rather than buckling. The specimens were not lined but no leaking was observed before the specimens fractured. The experimental compression failure stresses are seen to vary with the ratio of circumferential to axial applied stresses with the maximum observed strength occurring at a stress ratio around $SR = -2/-1$.

6. COMPARISON OF THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Theoretical biaxial failure envelopes were calculated for comparison with the experimental data. Each of the five conventional failure criteria mentioned previously and the simple maximum stress progressive failure model were used, coupled with the non-linear laminate modelling scheme and the lamina properties, determined from a completely different set of uniaxial tests, Table 1. Two separate envelopes were computed for the Tsai-Wu criterion taking the value of the interaction coefficients as $F_{XY}^* = 0$ and then as $F_{XY}^* = -0.5$.

$\pm 75^\circ$ Failure envelopes

Theoretical predictions using the five conventional failure criteria are plotted against the experimental fracture stresses results for $\pm 75^\circ$ filament wound tubes in Fig 3. There is a wide variation between the criteria, for instance, the predicted circumferential strength in open ended burst tests (ie axial stress zero) ranges from 730MPa (Hill) to 1240MPa (Max Stress or Schneider).

Whereas the Maximum Stress and Schneider criteria are in broad agreement with the experimental data, the Hill and Tsai-Wu criteria are conservative, and the maximum strain criterion gives an incorrect envelope shape (conservative in some parts and very optimistic in other parts).

The conventional Maximum Stress criterion and the progressive failure variant are plotted against the same experimental results in Fig 4. The two criteria overlap for the most part, indicating that 'initial' and 'final' failure are coincident events. For the region where the hoop to axial stress ratio (SR) lies between 0:1 and 16:1, the initial (transverse tensile cracking) and final (in-plane shear) failure modes are separated by an apparently small amount.

However, this is actually a significant effect, which is illustrated in Fig 4 by observing the predicted failure strengths for a biaxial load ratio of 10:1. The load vector cuts the conventional Maximum Stress envelope at (550:50) and the progressive failure envelope at (1150:115) is more than a factor of 2 difference. The strength predictions are very sensitive to biaxial stress ratio in this region, because of the elongated envelope shape which applies to the $\pm 75^\circ$ layup. The experimental results lie in-between the conventional and progressive predictions.

$\pm 55^\circ$ Failure envelope

The experimental results for the $\pm 55^\circ$ tubes are shown in Fig 5, along with the predicted failure envelopes using the five conventional failure criteria. The five conventional failure criteria are, without exception, very conservative. A small region exists in the compression/tension quadrant where the theories appear optimistic. In this region, the experimental results for the thin tubes are less than the theoretical results because of the influence of shell buckling.

Fig 3 Biaxial failure envelopes for $\pm 75^\circ$ GRP tubes (initial failure)

Fig 4 Biaxial failure envelopes for $\pm 75^\circ$ GRP tubes (final failure)

Fig 5 Biaxial failure envelopes for $\pm 55^\circ$ GRP tubes (initial failure)

Experimental results for thicker walled tubes, which fail by crushing rather than by buckling are included in Figs(4,6,8) for all the three laminates.

The same experimental results are compared with the conventional Maximum Stress criterion and the simple progressive failure variant in Fig 6. The shapes of the predicted envelopes bear some resemblance to the experimental leakage failure envelope, but the predicted initial failure stresses are lower than the experimental leakage stresses in the tension/tension quadrant. For the particular ratio of circumferential axial stresses of 2:1 for which this type of tube is often employed the maximum stress theory predicts initial failure (resin cracks) at a hoop stress of 71MPa. Leakage was observed to occur at hoop stress of 280MPa and final fracture did not occur until the hoop stress reached 736MPa (an order of magnitude higher than the predicted initial failure stress).

Fig 6 Biaxial failure envelope for $\pm 55^\circ$ tubes (final failure)

The envelope predicted by the progressive failure criterion is much closer to the experimental data in scale, but it is optimistic for hoop to axial stress ratios between 4:3 and 3:1, and it is pessimistic for ratios between 3:1 and 4:-1. In effect, a portion of the predicted envelope would appear to need a clockwise rotation, to line it up with the experimental data.

In the compression-compression quadrant, the theoretical initial and final failure predictions are coincident for stress ratios between 0:-1 and -1:-1 and between around -2:-1 and -1:0 and generally the predicted failure envelope in this quadrant has a similar form to that for the measured crushing strengths. The biaxial strength values for stress ratios between -1:-1 and -2:-1 depend strongly on the lamina longitudinal compressive strength. For the results shown in Fig(6), the theoretical curve was produced for a uniaxial lamina compressive strength parallel to the fibre of -950MPa rather than the value of -525MPa shown in Table 1. This value of -950 MPa was based on an investigation carried out recently at DRA on specimens with $V_f=70\%$.

$\pm 45^\circ$ Failure envelope

The theoretical failure envelopes predicted by the five conventional failure criteria are shown along with the experimental results for the $\pm 45^\circ$ tube in Fig 7. Again the five conventional failure criteria are, very conservative. The predicted failure stresses bear little resemblance to the experimental data in shape or scale. For a hoop to axial stress ratio of 1:1, the best theoretical criterion under-predicts the experimental values by a factor of 4 for 'leakage' failure and by a

Fig 7 Biaxial failure envelopes for $\pm 45^\circ$ GRP tubes (initial failure)

factor of 10 for 'ultimate' failure.

The experimental results are compared with the conventional Maximum Stress criterion and the simple progressive failure variant in Fig 8. The progressive failure variant clearly fits the form and scale of the experimental data far better than the conventional Maximum Stress criterion, however it is optimistic for hoop to axial stress ratios between 2:3 and 3:2, and it is pessimistic for ratios between 3:1.9 and 5:-3.

Fig 8 Biaxial failure envelopes for $\pm 45^\circ$ GRP tubes (final failure)

A portion of the predicted envelope would appear to need a clockwise rotation and a slight reduction in scale, to line up with the experimental data. This is probably partly due to the large change in shape of the specimen under load, which was not allowed for when calculating the experimental results.

7 DISCUSSION

The progressive failure modelling concept appears to be a significant advance on initial failure theories. Although the correlation with experimental data is imperfect in parts, Figs 4, 6 and 8 show clearly that the envelopes predicted are of the right form and scale. In view of the simplistic assumptions which were used to construct this particular progressive failure model, the results are encouraging and they justify further investigation of more refined progressive failure algorithms. Areas for improvement which can be identified immediately are:-

I. After first failure of a lamina in a transverse tension mode (resulting in cracks running parallel to the fibre direction) the simplistic model assumed that intralaminar shear forces can still be supported while the transverse stress is set to zero. Also, if the first mode is intralaminar shear, it is assumed that the failed lamina can carry transverse load while the shear stress is set to zero. In practise, the onset of transverse tensile failure, for example, is usually accompanied by microcracking, which increases in crack density if the loading is increased. The net result is a benign failure process whereby the transverse modulus gradually falls as a function of the strain level reached beyond that to initiate microcracks. A number of crack growth models have been postulated (e.g [7,8]) but none of these have been generalised to include stress interactions. In fact, the current models are limited to states of stress acting normally to the fibres (eg a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ crossply under uniaxial or biaxial tension). It is a big step to move from the current position to develop an accurate, fully generalised algorithm capable of predicting the residual values of E_T , ν_{TL} and G_{LT} in a cracked laminate but attempts are being made to do so.

II. A fundamental assumption of laminate theory is that a lamina, when subjected to a given combination of stress (ie σ_L , σ_T and τ_{LT}), behaves identically, whether it is within a unidirectional laminate or within a multidirectional laminate. Therefore, it is considered sufficient to characterise the lamina by a series of tests on unidirectional specimens to derive a data set, such as that listed in Table 1, which is then used with laminate theory to calculate the response of multidirectional laminates under multiaxial states of stress. There is now a growing awareness that a lamina may not have a unique set of strengths- they will be influenced

by the layup configuration within which the lamina is situated. Experimental evidence for this can be found in Refs[9,10] which showed that the transverse strength and strain to failure of glass/epoxy laminae varied in uniaxial tensile tests on $0^\circ/90^\circ$ crossply laminates as a function of the relative proportions of 0° and 90° laminae, and the ways in which the 90° laminae were distributed within the laminate. The explanation for the observed behaviour is that, in practise, a 3-D stress state is generated in angle ply laminates even when loaded in uniaxial tension. The magnitudes of the stress are dependent on stacking sequence and relative layer thicknesses, the general effect being that a lamina sandwiched between laminae of differing orientation suffers a constraint on lateral or through-thickness deformation.

8 CONCLUSIONS

-A piecewise non-linear variant of 2-D classical laminate theory has been used to take into account non-linear lamina stress-strain responses when calculating laminate behaviour.

-Five widely used theoretical failure criteria for FRP laminates have been tested against biaxial experimental data. They have been shown to be highly conservative, under-predicting ultimate strength of filament wound tubes by a factor of 10 in some cases.

-The simple progressive failure model gave better fit to the experimental ultimate strength data than the conventional initial failure criteria. The promising results obtained with this very simple version of a progressive failure model is an encouragement to pursue further refinements.

-The recently derived experimental results for biaxial compression strength extend the range of experimental strength results available for $\pm 55^\circ$ winding angle glass epoxy tubes and should be useful for further verification of failure theories.

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